

tional yield trials at seven locations throughout India, performance was encouraging. Overall performance indicates yields 13.7% higher than IR20.

MDU3 is semidwarf with high tillering ability and is nonlodging. It matures in 120-125 d, 5-10 d earlier than IR20, and has high productivity per day. The grain is long and slender with white rice; cooking quality is good.

ACM8 was screened under artificial as well as field conditions for the important pests and diseases (Table 2). It is highly resistant to GM; resistant to brown planthopper (BPH), leaffolder, and blast and moderately resistant to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) and brown leaf spot. ■

Table 2. Reaction to major insect pests and diseases at Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Pest	Score ^a	
	ACM8 (MDU3)	IR20
BPH (screenhouse)	3	7
WBPH (screenhouse)	5	7
Gall midge		
Screenhouse	0	7
Field	0	9
Leaffolder	3	7
Blast (field)		
Leaf	3	3
Neck	3	5
Brown leaf spot (field)	5	3
Sheath rot (field)	3	3

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Using rice nurseries to collect thrips for use in screening rice germplasm

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Breeding for resistance to thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) has lagged because of the lack of large pest numbers needed for screening germplasm.

Greenhouse cultures have failed to provide the thousands of thrips needed.

We developed a simple technique to collect thrips directly from rice nurseries. The nurseries are sown every 2 wk during peak thrips incidence.

Pregerminated IR64 seed was sown in 7- × 1-m beds Aug-Oct 1988 in Coimbatore. At 10, 20, and 30 d after sowing (DAS), seedlings were examined under a binocular microscope. Thrips population/seedling was 5-6 adults at 10 DAS, 60-70

nymphs at 20 DAS, and 75-80 adults at 30 DAS. Thrips nymphs were mopped up at 20 DAS by passing a wet palm 4-5 times across seedlings in the nursery and freed by dipping the hand in a pail of water (see figure). We collected 200-250 thrips per sweep.

Water containing thrips collected per 25 sweeps was poured uniformly on 7-d-old seedlings of test cultivars (including resistant Ptb 21 and susceptible TN1) grown in wooden trays (60 × 40 × 10 cm) inside a large water-filled iron tray. Each seedling was infested with 5-6 nymphs.

Alternatively, water containing thrips was poured on 30-d-old TN1 plants kept inside a water-filled tray. Nymphs settled readily on TN1 plants, which were then tapped gently over seedling trays for infestation. Using thrips collected this way, we were able to screen 400 entries for resistance. The technique can be used in areas where dry weather prevails for 3-4 mo. Thrips populations peak with the onset of dry weather; heavy rains wash them away. ■

Pest resistance—other pests

Reaction of rice cultivar Faro 11 to sugarcane cyst nematode *Heterodera sacchari*

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H. sacchari (Luc and Merny) is widespread in sugarcane cropping areas of Nigeria. In many of the mid-belt states of Nigeria, rice and sugarcane are intercropped or relay-cropped. In earlier screening of some rice varieties, all were susceptible to *H. sacchari*. We studied *H. sacchari* pathogenicity on rice.

Ten-liter plastic buckets were filled with soil collected from an *H. sacchari*-endemic field at the Nigerian Sugar Company plantation, Bacita, and planted with rice cultivar Faro 11. Inocula were juveniles emerging from cysts collected earlier from the same field using a

Schematic of procedure for collecting rice thrips from nurseries to use in screening rice germplasm for thrips resistance.